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Analysis of the family social climate among communities in Colombia, Cuba and Perú.

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Abstract (in English): Families, as the basic nucleus of society, promote the development of diverse personal skills. In this context, this study analyzed the family social climate in communities in Colombia, Cuba and Peru. For this purpose, a qualitative approach was used and interviews were conducted with the participation of five families from each country. It was found that migration is a frequent phenomenon that has affected both the structure and dynamics of families, testing their resilience. There have been advances in parenting styles, which are more democratic, encouraging children's autonomy and the expression of emotions. In addition, there is greater participation of women in supporting the household.

Keywords: Family social climate, Family climate, Family, Intrafamily relationships, cultures.

Introduction.

The family, according to Scorsolini (2022), is characterized as the set of individuals united by biological, legal, and cultural ties. In addition, by providing meaningful events through parenting, it influences the integral development of its members (Acuña et al., 2020). In this process, children internalize behaviors that they then replicate by establishing their own families (Gallego et al., 2019). However, it is important to note that specific social factors can influence family functioning (Abufhele & Jeanneret, 2020), triggering changes in its structure and dynamics (Scorsolini, 2022).

However, at present, statistics have been reported that show adverse situations within the family environment in the Latin American context, which have a negative impact on its dynamics and functioning. In this context, domestic violence is one of the most widespread problems in the family environment, affecting around one in three women in the world (World Health Organization (WHO), 2021). In fact, it is considered a current public health problem that needs collective attention by health authorities, governments, and society as a whole (Mayor et al., 2019).

In this sense, statistics that have been reported in the context of Peru, Colombia and Cuba were identified. In Peru, according to the National Comprehensive Program for the Bienestar Familiar (INABIF, 2016),

In the face of family conflicts, 29% of couples fail to agree on opinions, 18% do not seek solutions, 6% avoid the subject and 5% resort to physical and verbal violence. In addition, 28% do not consider the opinions of their children, 25% lack intra-family communication and 22% physically abuse their children.

In the Colombian context, it is no stranger to these problems, as evidenced by the fact that in 2020, 123,759 complaints were registered in the family context (National Institute of Legal Medicine and Forensic Sciences of Colombia, 2020). In addition, according to the study by Serna et al. (2020), carried out in schoolchildren in Quindío, Colombia, it was found that 46.3% belonged to dysfunctional families, which was associated with a higher probability of depression. In addition, in 2020, 123,759 complaints were registered in the family context, according to the National Institute of Legal Medicine and Forensic Sciences of Colombia (2020). In similar research, Galvis et al. (2022) studied 20 families from the Barrio de Cormoranes, Colombia, and found that 89% of them were characterized by low family functioning, while only 11% showed a high level of functioning.

Similarly, in the Cuban context, according to the study carried out by Herrezuelo et al. (2021), 43.6% of the victims were between the ages of 20 and 35. In addition, 53.4% of those affected were domestic workers, with physical violence standing out as the most prevalent form of physical violence. In addition, according to Betancourt & Gross (2018), families experience changes in their dynamics and structure when migrating, facing significant conflicts and adapting with new forms of behavior and communication. In Cuba, through research in which 519 children participated, it was identified that 70% belonged to dysfunctional families.

Considering the above, it is crucial to analyze the family social climate in the context of three Latin American countries, since it constitutes a significant variable to understand family dynamics. Likewise, it is defined as the result of the perceptions and situations shared by families and consists of the way in which parents relate and communicate with their children (Moss, 1974), influencing their psychosocial well-being (Moreno et al., 2009).

Therefore, it is important to provide positive experiences in the family environment, however, there are parents who present unhealthy behaviors such as alcohol consumption, causing students to develop negative perceptions about their family environment (Iacopetti et al., 2021).

In this way, Moss (1974) proposed three fundamental dimensions for the understanding of the family social climate. The first, called "Development", refers to the way in which the family contributes to the growth and development of its members. The second dimension called "Stability", which addresses the degree of emotional stability and security within the family. The third dimension called "Family Relationships", which consists of the quality of interactions between family members and cohesion within the home. In this sense, he developed the

family social climate scale in 1981. In fact, Kurock et al. (2022) underline the importance of considering these dimensions during the analysis of family social climate.

Due to the increase in problems and the complexity of the family context, the need arises to understand this construct from the perspective of three countries. This will allow to obtain a deep understanding of the cultural and contextual phenomena that affect families in each country and to detect changes in family structure and dynamics. This research is designed to answer the following question: What are the characteristics of the family social climate in Peru, Colombia and Cuba?

The study is justified at the theoretical level, because it provides relevant information that allows understanding the study variable; and at a practical level, because through the contributions provided, the development of prevention procedures will be promoted and the dynamics of families in the countries of Colombia, Cuba and Peru will be improved.

Thus, this study aimed to analyze the family social climate among the communities of Colombia, Cuba and Peru. Specifically, the following were established: to compare family relations between communities in Colombia, Cuba, and Peru; to compare stability in the families of the communities of Colombia, Cuba and Peru; and to compare the development of families in communities in Colombia, Cuba and Peru.

Method.

• Research design

A qualitative approach was used with the aim of understanding certain phenomena from the perspective of the participants (Martínez, 2004). It is also characterized by having an ethnographic design, which consists of the analysis of the social and cultural behaviors of a community (Salgado, 2007).

•Participants

In this study, interviews were conducted with participants of both sexes, over 18 years of age, from families belonging to communities in Colombia, Peru and Cuba. A total of 15 families were worked on, distributed equally among the three countries mentioned: Colombia, Peru and Cuba. As for Colombia, the sample consisted of 5 families from the Toez Reservation in Cali, where approximately 250 families and an average of 800 people reside. On the Cuban side, 5 families from the community of Cojimar, in the province of Havana, were selected. In the case of Peru, 5 families were taken from the community of Simbilá, in Piura, where an average of 837 families live.

With respect to ethical aspects, informed consent was provided to the participants, specifying the procedures to be carried out and guaranteeing a safe and respectful environment for the development of the interviews. The right of participants to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences was detailed, ensuring the confidentiality and anonymity of the data. The data were analyzed and reported in a framework of transparency and honesty, without manipulation or falsification of any kind.

• Data collection tools and techniques

Considering the recommendations of Hernández-Sampieri and Mendoza (2018), the interview technique was used, using as an instrument a structured interview based on the family social climate scale (FES) developed by R. H. Moos, B. S. Moos and E. J. Trickett. This tool aims to assess the family social climate through the dimensions of family relationships, family development, and family stability. It is relevant to note that the interview was subjected to analysis by 5 experts with experience in qualitative research and in relation to the study variable. Therefore, this process allowed the selection of items that were representative of the constructed evaluated.

- Procedure

First, the Family Social Climate Scale (FES), which guided the development of the interviews, was analyzed by a group of experts in qualitative research to ensure its relevance and clarity. Subsequently, the dates and times to visit the families in their homes were coordinated; In addition, the purpose of the study was explained, the confidentiality of the information and the indications to be followed during the interview were provided. In this sense, informed consent was requested for voluntary participation, specifying that the interviews would be recorded. The interviews lasted two hours and the researchers maintained an impartial attitude to obtain data with the least possible degree of bias. Finally, the recorded information was transcribed and analyzed using a qualitative program.

- Data Analytics Strategy

The interviews, previously recorded in audio format, were transcribed verbatim. Subsequently, a qualitative analysis was carried out through the MAXQDA program in its 2020 version, which consisted of a thematic analysis. This analysis was developed in several stages: first, a reading of the transcribed interviews was carried out, during which important fragments were underlined and memos were assigned. Second, the thematic categories were established. Third, while the text was being revised, a category was assigned to each relevant line. Fourth, the highlighted fragments were grouped under the same categories. Fifth, subcategories were defined and, finally, the analysis by categories and the presentation of the results were carried out.

Table 1. *Analysis of the relationship dimension in the Colombia, Cuba and Peru cultures.*

Dimensions	Colombia	Cuba	Perú	Comparative analysis
Cohesion	Families are supported by an economic level, work and household functions; however, there have been variations, as family members move to other places for economic reasons and young people have other interests.	There is an emotional, economic and household support; however, migration and the formation of other families have generated changes in the dynamics, but family unity is maintained	Family supports each other emotionally and by talking and giving each other words of encouragement. They also contribute financially by selling handicrafts, chicha de jora and traditional food. In addition, they work together in household chores. However, some family members chose to move to the capital in search of better life opportunities.	In all three countries, some family members are migrating, whether for reasons of establishing their own home, work or study, which has changed the dynamics of mutual support. Despite this separation, they have looked for ways to maintain a regular connection and strengthen family bonds.
Expressiveness	There is freedom of emotional expression for all members of the family. This is a significant change, given that previously, there was priority in the emotional expression of	They express their joy freely and anger in an assertive way, as they seek to establish agreements. In some families, it is observed that there may be	Members can express their feelings freely. Some families have a specific day, such as Sundays, to talk openly about how they are feeling. Although in the past the authority of grandparents used	Families have evolved, observing a change in the way of parenting that has led to greater freedom in emotional expression. Although in some families, there is still difficulty expressing their emotions as a result of strict parenting.

	adults. Although, it depends on each family structure, well, there are families, which has always existed the freedom to express their feelings.	difficulties expressing words of affection.	in to be highly respected, today of children can express their opinions without permission of the family.	
Conflict	When problematic behaviors arise in the family, it is common to seek the help of a traditional doctor in search of remedies, and even to resort to physical punishment or impose mandatory activities for several years as a corrective measure. In more serious situations, such as crimes, the alternative is usually to resort to the prosecutor's office. However, over time, this dynamic has evolved. In particular, young families have chosen to adopt other strategies to address conflicts, focusing on dialogue and communication.	In the face of conflicts, they establish agreements, explaining the reasons, maintaining authority, but without losing respect.	When a conflict arises, they focus on verbally expressing their feelings in a respectful way, seeking to reach an agreement. In the past, previous generations used to resort to aggressive methods, such as the use of the whip, but today that has changed.	There has been a shift in the way conflicts are addressed in the three countries. Today, young families tend to resolve family problems through dialogue, in contrast to the use of physical punishment as a method of resolution that was prevalent in the past. However, there are still families who opt for this strategy to resolve their conflicts.

Table 2. Analysis of the development dimension in families in Colombia, Cuba and Peru.

Dimensions	Colombia	Cuba	Perú	Analysis
Autonomy	Children usually become independent when they decide to form their own family. On some occasions, they live together for a few years in the home of the in-laws before establishing their own home. They may also become independent due to educational or	Families make decisions, which are respected, but the consequences must be assumed. Family members become independent when they form their own family or for academic and/or work matters.	From a young age, children collaborate in household chores. Women usually help with cooking and cleaning, while men are in charge of jobs that require strength and energy. As they	Its often observed that children become independent when they decide to start their own family, study or work. In the past, these decisions needed parental approval, but today there is more freedom, as long as children are willing

	work reasons. However, changes in this dynamic have been observed over time. Previously, there used to be meaningful dialogue when making these decisions, but today, this communication has diminished.		grow older and reach youth, they begin to make decisions for themselves. Some choose to become independent early, form a couple and even have children on some occasions.	to take the consequences and learn from them.
Performance	The family activities that are maintained during Christmas, Mother's Day, birthdays, the Minga, Cabildo and agriculture. However, the frequency of meetings and agriculture has decreased. This is associated with new families that are made up of couples with different traditions.	Family activities that are maintained over time consist of: Mother's Day, birthdays, Christmas and family gatherings. There have been variations as a result of the migration of certain family members or those who formed their own family.	The family activities that are still maintained in families are: Christmas parties, New Year's party, Mother's Day, Father's Day, July 28 and Father's birthday parties.	Colombia, Cuba and Peru, families maintain activities such as: family gatherings at Christmas, Mother's Day, birthdays. However, in Colombia, there are traditions such as the Minga, Cabildo and agriculture.
Intellectual cultural social recreational	Families participate in cultural events such as the possession of the Cabildo, the Minga, Cxha puç (offering season), the saakhelu (seed ritual), the kúcxwala á te (time of the big black), and the kwet wuwu (harmonization of the staff). However, the frequency of participation of some families has decreased, leading to the disappearance of rituals and myths.	Families do not participate in cultural activities, expressing their dissatisfaction, since years ago there were places of their own for events of this type, but today they have other functions. The practice of fishing activities has been lost.	Families join in their town's cultural and anniversary celebrations in honor of Señor Cautivo, San Martín de Porres and local traditional fairs. In the past, generations used to participate in the festivities of the Virgin of Perpetual Help, but with the passage of time this celebration disappeared.	In Colombia and Peru, families still participate in cultural activities. Cuba, however, do not participate in cultural activities. In both families, cultural events have been lost.
Morality- Religiosity	Families practice religions such as Catholic, Evangelical, Pentecostal; likewise, ritual practices such as: Nasa yat culture; Customs and rituals such as: annual ritual practices such as the çxha puç (season of offering), the	Families are Catholic, however, there are other types of religion. There is no religious fanaticism.	Families practice religions such as Catholicism for the most part, but one sector is evangelical and Protestant.	Colombia, Peru and Cuba families practice both the Catholic and Evangelical religions. In Colombia, a decrease in the practice of religious rituals has been

saakhelu (ritual of the seed), the kúcxwala a te (time of the great black), and the kwet wuwu (harmonization of the staff).	observed. On the other hand, in Cuba, there is no perceived religious fanaticism. significant in families.
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Table 3 Analysis of the stability dimension in families in Colombia, Cuba y Perú.

Dimensions	Colombia	Cuba	Perú	Comparative analysis
Organization	There are extended, nuclear and single-parent families. With respect to household functions, the father provides the sustenance of the home, although at present, more job opportunities are offered to women. The children dedicate themselves to studying, although there are cases in which they dedicate themselves to work.	Families encourage each member to fulfill a function in the home. Women are in charge of domestic activities and men are in charge of strength activities.	There are mostly extended families where grandparents, grandchildren live at home who share the same home, where each one has their own space	Colombia, Peru and Cuba, there are nuclear, extended and single-parent families. Traditionally, men were the main breadwinners, but today, women also have that opportunity. In general, children dedicate themselves to study and collaborate in household chores, although those who do not study choose to work or help at home.
Control	Family practices values such as ethics, respect, union, and communication, which influence the behavior of the members. Although, they have been lost over time.	Respect, honesty, affection and cleanliness are rules that are maintained in families; although, over the years there have been certain modifications in the way of expressing oneself.	Families maintain their own rules in order to maintain authority, order and control. The family unit is what predominates	Colombia, Cuba, and Peru, family rules focus on respect, union, affection, and communication. However, the latter has been affected by the separation of members who form their own families in other cities, immigration and travel for economic and work reasons.

Discussion.

The family environment is recognized as the primordial nucleus where significant experiences are forged that shape the learning of fundamental behaviors for life (Suarez & Vélez, 2018). Consequently, children internalize patterns of interaction within the family, which implies that these behaviors will be replicated when they themselves constitute their own families (Gallego et al., 2019). It also plays a crucial role in transmitting cultural heritage from one generation to another, involving the teaching of traditions and ways of life that have been fundamental to the family over time (Ruiz, 2004). In fact, the intergenerational transmission of parental ties can influence the learning of maladaptive behaviors (Mannarini et al., 2018). In addition, in certain cultures, there is a more pronounced inclination towards the transmission of certain parental behaviors that could trigger behavioral problems in children (Rothenberg et al., 2023).

Therefore, there is a need to gain a deep understanding of the family in which the particularities of each family are considered. In this context, the family social climate among communities in Colombia, Cuba and Peru was analyzed, using a sample of 15 families, distributed equally with 4 representatives from each country. In this sense, interview processes were carried out based on the Family Social Climate (FES) questionnaire.

In the first category "relationships", it has been found that in the three countries studied, a pattern of migration of family members in search of independence is observed, which has altered the dynamics of mutual support. Despite this separation, ways have been sought to maintain a regular connection and strengthen family bonds. Regarding expressiveness, there has been an evolution in parenting, resulting in greater emotional freedom, although difficulties persist in some families due to strict parenting. As for the conflict, there has been a change in the way it is addressed, where young families opt for dialogue instead of physical punishment, although there are still families that resort to the latter strategy. In fact, the way in which families relate to each other and resolve conflicts has undergone significant changes due to phenomena such as migration, which alter family dynamics and structure, generating challenges and adaptations in behaviors and communication (Betancourt & Gross, 2018). In addition, these changes are influenced by parenting styles (Strayer & Roberts, 2004; Morris et al., 2007; Castro et al., 2015; Mejía, 2020). Therefore, it seeks to promote effective communication to reduce the incidence of adverse events (Ginsburg et al., 2007; López-Martínez et al., 2019), since it has been shown that dysfunctional families increase the risk of mental disorders (Saarinen et al., 2023) and eating behavior problems (White et al., 2019).

In the "development" category, it has been noted that children often choose to become independent when deciding to start their own family, study or work. In the past, these decisions were subject to parental approval, but today there is greater freedom. In addition, families still maintain deep-rooted traditions, such as family gatherings at Christmas, Mother's Day, and birthdays. However, in Colombia, additional activities such as the Minga, the Cabildo and agriculture are practiced. Regarding cultural activities, both Colombia and Peru continue to participate, although in Cuba there is less involvement. In addition, in Colombia, Peru and Cuba, the Catholic and Evangelical religions predominate, but there is also a presence of religions such as Pentecostal and Protestant. Each country, however, has its particularities; for example, in Colombia, religious rituals are present, but they are in decline, while in Cuba there is no significant religious fervor.

In this context, there is evidence of an increase in respect for the decisions of the children to become independent, due to the fact that families are more capable. In fact, an association has been established between the level of autonomy of young people and the role of the family, highlighting the importance of assigning responsibilities to children to promote their autonomy (Bernal et al., 2020). A high family dependence on the part of children can be limiting to their development (Santander & Rojas, 2020). It was also identified that the Catholic and Evangelical religions predominate. There is evidence that the practice of religion decreases the likelihood that adolescents will develop risky behaviors that may affect their psychological well-being (Rajab et al., 2021).

In the third category, "stability", it is observed that in Colombia, Peru and Cuba nuclear, extended and single-parent families coexist. In the past, the family support fell mainly on men, but today women also assume this role. In general, children dedicate themselves to study and collaborate in household chores, although those who do not study choose to work or help at home. In these countries, family norms focus on respect, togetherness, affection, and communication. However, the latter has been affected by the separation of members who form their own families in other cities, immigration and travel for economic and work reasons. In this context, the fundamental role played by the family as the primary group where various behaviors associated with values, customs, and norms essential to face challenges are internalized, is recognized. However, in recent years, a modification in family dynamics and structures has been observed, which has led to the emergence of antisocial behaviors within families (Díaz et al., 2020; Brizuela et al., 2021).

Conclusions.

The results obtained in this research offer valuable contributions to the disciplinary knowledge of the dynamics of the family social climate in diverse cultural contexts, focusing particularly on the communities of Colombia, Cuba and Peru. This study not only enriches the existing understanding in the discipline, but also contributes to the literature by providing a contextualized view of the factors that influence the family social climate within the Latin American context. In this way, a significant perspective is added to the analysis of the complexities and particularities that characterize family dynamics in these regions. However, it is essential to recognize that these findings specifically represent the selected communities in Colombia, Cuba, and Peru, and should not be extrapolated to other cultures without further analysis.

The implications of this study underscore the imperative need to design culturally sensitive family policies and practices. It also highlights the importance of future research to delve into the influence of culture on family dynamics, with the aim of developing more precise and effective intervention strategies. These findings emphasize the relevance of addressing cultural diversities by formulating approaches and programs that promote family well-being in a more targeted and contextualized way.

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